

PHYSIOLOGICAL-BIOCHEMICAL AND MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF LEMON**Khudayarova S.I.**

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Relevance: In this article, I will provide you with information about citrus fruits that we all love to eat, which are widely distributed worldwide and rich in vitamins beneficial for our body. To discuss the nutritional and therapeutic-prophylactic properties of lemons, a lot of information about its chemical composition has been collected in the literature.

The purpose of the study: The socio-economic stability in the region is largely determined by the standard of living of all segments of the population, primarily the level of human satisfaction with food products. One of the main links in food production is fruit growing, the level of development of which depends on the types of fruits and berries necessary for maintaining human health.

Methods and techniques: The purpose of this work is to study the bioecological properties of sour lemon and to develop effective measures to increase its yield under protected soil conditions.

Results: The chemical nature of phytoncides is complex and still poorly understood. It was established that citric acid phytoncides consist of a mixture of various substances, among which the identified ones are essential oils (geranyl acetate, limonene, citral), flavonoids (gesperidine, naringin), aldehydes, cyanoic acid, etc. Flavonoids (gesperidin, naringin), aldehydes, cyanoic acid, etc. The biological activity of phytoncides is usually explained not by a single known substance, but by the unity of all substances. The phytoncidal properties of volatile fractions of phytoncides and tissue juice are distinguished. Phytoncides are widely used in medicine. They have antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties, and can have an antihelminth and antiviral, anti-allergic, and immunostimulating effect. Some phytoncides have a normalizing effect on the cardiovascular system, stimulate the motor secretory activity of the gastrointestinal tract, and have a sedative effect on it. Plant medicinal preparations containing phytoncides are called phytoncides, which differ in their chemical composition and pharmacological properties.

Conclusion: In domestic and foreign literature, information on the influence of environmental conditions on the storability of fruits, the accumulation and storage of the main components of their chemical composition is limited. The study of physiological and biochemical changes occurring in ripening and stored fruits makes it possible to theoretically substantiate the optimal storage periods and regime for their introduction into the national economy. All metabolic processes occurring in plants are associated with respiration, therefore its activity is, in a certain sense, the most important factor determining the shelf life of fruits. Lemon is also rich in pectins. They are especially abundant in fruit peels, where pectins make up ~20-40% of all dry matter.